

Optimizing Polycaprolactone Coating on WE43 Magnesium Alloy for Biodegradable Stent Applications: A Comprehensive Study Using Dual Solvents, Ultrasonic Atomization Spray, and Anodization Techniques

Seyed Masih Mousavizadeh^a, Mingzhi Yu^a, Michael D. Gilchrist^a and Nan Zhang^{a*}

^a*Centre of Micro/Nano Manufacturing Technology (MNMT-Dublin), School of Mechanical & Materials Engineering, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland*

Abstract

WE43 magnesium-based alloy is modified and investigated for biodegradable gene-eluting stent applications as it is an ideal engineering material with good mechanical properties and offers better biocompatibility compared to aluminium/zinc (AZ) alloys. In this work, polycaprolactone (PCL) is coated on WE43 using two different solvents via ultrasonic atomization spray coating. For better adhesion of this PCL to the surface, anodization was performed on WE43 to increase bonding strength. Spray coating parameters such as solution concentration, number of spray passes, atomizing power, etc., were optimised for best coating performance. Characterizations on the coatings showed that both acetone and dichloromethane are suitable for spray coating PCL, but acetone is slightly better, and it is also safer and easier to use. The porous microstructure of oxides formed by anodization increased the bonding adhesion between PCL and WE43. PCL covering these oxides led to enhanced anticorrosion properties as this hydrophobic polymer decreased the water uptake and increased the corrosion resistance. This significantly enhanced corrosion resistance also maintains the mechanical properties of the WE43 as the mass loss decreased by a factor of four times after PCL coating, helping to keep the mechanical integrity of WE43. Having the oxide layer beneath PCL coating prevented it from peeling off. Subsequent in vitro cell viability results showed that the PCL layer enhanced the viability of HAoEC cells.

Keywords: Spray coating, Polycaprolactone, WE43, Stent, Cell viability

1. Introduction

Biodegradable materials are increasingly preferred for cardiovascular applications, as they offer the advantage of avoiding long-term complications associated with permanent implants [2]. The need for biodegradable stents is transient, as they only play a crucial role during the initial support phase, after which the artery undergoes remodeling [9]. Consequently, there is an increasing use of stents manufactured from biodegradable polymers or metals [6, 8]. An ideal biodegradable stent serves as mechanical support during the resolution of arterial blockage and subsequently degrades without causing irritation, inflammation, or any adverse effects on the human body [17, 3].

Magnesium (Mg) alloys have garnered significant attention in recent years due to their exceptional mechanical properties and biodegradability [15]. Among these, WE43, a high-strength Mg alloy, is preferred over AZ alloys as it is aluminium-free, which is known to be neurotoxic and linked to dementia and Alzheimer's disease [27, 5, 7]. However, WE43 cannot be used as a bare metal stent due to the occurrence of restenosis caused by coronary interaction with the stent. Additionally, its inherent reactivity and poor corrosion resistance limit its use as a biomaterial [1, 11]. To address these challenges, surface modification techniques such as PEO (Plasma Electrolytic Oxidation)/MAO (Micro-Arc Oxidation), anodization, polymer coatings, etc., have emerged as viable solutions [29].

Among various polymer candidates, FDA-approved polycaprolactone (PCL) is a versatile and biocompatible material for surface coating applications. Its desirable properties, including biodegradability, low toxicity, and hydrophobicity, make it an attractive option for enhancing the surface properties of magnesium alloys [24, 10].

There are many available methods for coating polymers, such as spin coating, bar coating, inkjet printing, and screen printing, but spray coating offers a distinct advantage. It enables the coating of three-dimensional microstructures like stents [4]. Here, using ultrasonic atomization is often preferred over pneumatic atomization, which uses high-frequency acoustic vibration to generate a fine mist of

*Corresponding author. School of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, University College Dublin, Belfield, Dublin, 4, Ireland
E-mail address: nan.zhang@ucd.ie (N. Zhang)

Figure 1: Schematic representation of spray coating setup.

coating solution [12]. In addition, ultrasonic atomization spray coating (UASC) offers several benefits: simplicity, high transfer efficiency, cost-effectiveness, precise conformal coating on both planar and nonplanar surfaces, generation of small droplets in the micrometre range, and consistent reproducibility [18, 19]. As seen in Fig 1, in spray coating, the process involves the formation of small droplets from a solution, followed by their deposition and merging on a substrate. The coating solution is atomized within the spray nozzle, resulting in the formation of small droplets. These droplets are then released onto a substrate beneath the spray nozzle, which results in the formation of a coating [23].

In spray coating, the final polymer coating is affected by many parameters which need to be optimized to achieve the desired properties, some of these are solvent selection, solution concentration, number of spray passes, polymer solution flow rate, atomizing power, the distance between the spray nozzle and substrate, and air pressure used to transport the sprayed droplets to the substrate [4]. The principal with using magnesium and its alloys as a stent is that they are susceptible to degradation in any aqueous environment with more than 30 mmol/l chloride content. This means that Mg corrodes in the body where the concentration of chloride is above 150 mmol/l. Magnesium reacts in such aqueous solutions as per reaction (1) [26]:

The evolved hydrogen can peel off any polymer coating from the surface. Hence, introducing an intermediary layer between the polymer coating and a Mg substrate

should significantly improve the adhesion and corrosion resistance of the polymer coating [25, 28]. Anodization treatment in a sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution can achieve a Mg/O transition layer with a rough structure [16].

The Mg/O layer has a high roughness and is suitable for interlocking the polymer layer as well as being a corrosion resistant. Reaction (2) shows what happens on the surface during anodization. Considering reactions (1) and (2), by having the Mg(OH)₂ on the surface, increasing the content of the reaction products in reaction (1), the reaction equilibrium changes, and the progress of the forward reaction is retarded. This ensures fewer hydrogen gas pockets can form and provides resistance against corrosion [21].

In the course of this investigation, modifications were made to the surface of WE43 to facilitate the application of a PCL coating. Anodization played an important role in enhancing adhesion, simultaneously serving as an additional protective layer against corrosion and hydrogen formation. Notably, this study introduces a novel approach by employing ultrasonic atomization spray coating to directly apply PCL onto WE43, a magnesium-based alloy deemed ideal for biodegradable platforms. The enhanced corrosion resistance and biocompatibility; resulting contribute to the efficacy of WE43 as a substrate for a gene/drug carrier layer. This work addresses how to use ultrasonic atomization spray to provide PCL with good bonding strength, thereby paving the way for improved functionality and potential advancements in cardiovascular treatment.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

PCL pellets (Mw = 80,000) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. The substrate was commercial WE43 with 1 mm-thick sheets containing 4% Y, 3.3% RE (Nd, Gd), and 0.5% Zr bought from Shanghai Metal Products Co., Ltd., China. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was purchased from AppliChem, Germany. Dichloromethane (Honeywell, USA) and Acetone (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) were used as solvents.

2.2. Preparation of Mg/O transition layer

For the anodization, samples (25mm×20mm) were cut out of the WE43 sheets. They were mechanically ground with silicon carbide abrasive paper up to No.

4000, rinsed with distilled water, and then dried with an airgun. These samples were labelled as W. 1M NaOH alkali solution with pH 13 was used for treatment. Anodization was performed at room temperature for 10 minutes. These samples (W/O) were then immersed in water ($\approx 100^\circ\text{C}$) for post-treatment and dried with an airgun.

2.3. Coating PCL

The coating was performed using a LULP500 ultrasonic liquid processor (Cheer-sonic Ultrasonic Co.) with an x-y axis. A nozzle with a diameter of 0.5 mm was used to produce an atomized spray. The nozzle was connected to a compressed air source and a LEGATO® 101 KD Scientific syringe pump. The air pressure was set at 80 psi, and the flow rate was 0.5ml/min. The distance between the nozzle and the samples was set at 60 mm, and the atomizing power was 0.18 A. The PCL concentration in the solvent was 1 wt%. These parameters showed the best results for the coated samples; therefore, they were kept as constant parameters during all the coatings. For the coating to be optimized, PCL was first applied to glass slides using two common solvents, acetone (ACE) and dichloromethane (DCM). The W/O samples were coated using different solvents and various PCL concentrations in different spray passes. After coating, the samples were incubated at 60°C for 24 hours as post-treatment. These various samples were separately labelled as W, W/O and W/O/P.

2.4. Coating characterization

Microstructural analysis was performed using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (Zeiss Sigma 300), and a Hitachi Topdesk 4000 was used for EDS analysis to characterize the layers formed on the surface. Cross-sectional images were taken to measure the coated layer thickness. X-ray diffractometry (XRD) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) were utilized to identify differences in sprayed PCL by different solvents. XRD (Inel-EQUINOX3000) with monochromatic Cu-K radiation was used. DSC was performed on sprayed coating (≈ 5 mg) using a NETZSCH Polyma 214. The samples were first cooled down to -100°C and then heated up 100°C and this was repeated once again in an argon atmosphere at a constant heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (ALPHA II FTIR) was performed in the range of $4000\text{-}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to determine the functional groups. 200 g/l CrO_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in demineralized water was used to remove the corrosion products from the samples to investigate corroded surfaces. The chemical composition of the corrosion products on the surface was investigated by X-ray photoelectron

spectroscopy (XPS, Kratos Axis Ultra DLD, USA) using an X-ray source of Al K α (1486.6 eV) with an elliptical spot size of 300 μm \times 700 μm . Roughness parameters were measured using a Mitutoyo SJ-410 surface roughness tester. Each parameter was measured five times, and the average was reported.

The static contact angle was measured using an Ossila contact angle goniometer with 5 μL water droplets. 3nh YG60 gloss meter was used to measure the opacity of the coating on the glass slides using 60° measuring angle. Cross-cut tape tests were performed to assess the adhesion of the PCL to the substrate by applying and removing pressure-sensitive tape over cuts made in the film according to ASTM D3359-22. A lattice pattern with six cuts in each direction was made on the film and removed by a pressure-sensitive tape. AmScope optical microscope and EDS mapping were used to check for coating detachments.

2.5. *In vitro* corrosion evaluation

2.5.1. *Electrochemical measurements*

Electrochemical tests were performed in PBS¹ (Fisher Scientific International, Inc) using potentiostat/galvanostat CS310 (Wuhan CorrTest Instruments Corp., Ltd., China) electrochemical interface. A Platinum sheet with an area of 100 mm² was used as the counter electrode and the reference electrode was an Ag/AgCl electrode in saturated KCl. Open circuit potential (Eoc) was monitored for the samples with an area of 100 mm² for 144 hours. Potentiodynamic polarization measurement (PDP) was carried out to evaluate the anti-corrosion performance of the samples. The electrode potential was scanned from +0.5 to -0.5 V versus the Eoc at a scan rate of 2 mV s⁻¹. CS Studio 6 software was used with the least squares method to fit the polarization curves obtained from the patterns. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) tests were performed in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 10 mHz, and the perturbation amplitude was 10 mV. The obtained experimental data were fitted with Zview software. Before the PDP and EIS tests, samples were immersed in PBS for 2 hours to achieve a steady open circuit potential (Eoc).

2.5.2. *Hydrogen measurement and immersion test*

The weight of the sample was recorded using an electronic microbalance. Subsequently, the samples, with an area of 9.42 cm², were placed into 50 mL centrifuge tubes containing 20 mL of PBS at 37°C. The pH level of the solution

¹Phosphate-buffered saline

within each tube was assessed and recorded daily for a period of 7 days. Following this 7-day period, 200 g/l CrO₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in demineralized water was used to remove the corrosion products from the samples to investigate corroded surfaces, followed by rinsing with distilled water and alcohol for 10 minutes. This process allowed for the calculation of mass loss, which was determined using the following formula:

$$\text{Mass loss} = \frac{m_0 - m_1}{s} \quad (3)$$

where m_0 and m_1 are the mass of samples before and after treatment, and s is the surface area of samples [13, 14]. The hydrogen evolution rate was measured using a customized setup where WE43 samples with an exposed area of 10 mm² were put in a beaker containing 100 ml of PBS (Fisher Scientific International, Inc). A funnel was placed over the specimen to ensure that all the hydrogen gas evolved from the surface of the sample was collected. A burette was mounted over the funnel and was initially full of the test solution. The hydrogen collected by the funnel bubbled into the burette and gradually displaced the test solution. In this way, the volume of the evolved hydrogen was measured by reading the level of the test solution in the burette [22]. To determine the influence of corrosion on specimen mechanical integrity, a 3-point bending test was performed according to ASTM E290. Different samples were immersed in PBS at 37°C for 7 days before the test.

2.6. Cell viability test

The Endothelial Cell Growth Medium, Trypsin-EDTA solution, and Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) were sourced from Merck Life Science (Darmstadt, Germany). Penicillin/streptomycin, Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), and the Alamar Blue Cell Viability Reagent were obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Human aortic endothelial cells (HAoEC) were used to assess in-vitro cell viability through an indirect method. Initially, all samples were cut into 10 mm × 10 mm × 1 mm sheets. These samples were immersed individually into 1 mL of Endothelial Cell Growth Medium without any Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and penicillin/streptomycin, and then placed in a cell culture incubator (maintained at 5% CO₂ and 37°C) for 72 hours. Following incubation, the solutions were transferred and centrifuged, and the supernatant fluid was collected and refrigerated at 4°C to serve as the extracts. HAoEC, with a density of 5 × 10³ cells, were seeded in a 96-well plate containing Endothelial Cell Growth Medium supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin- streptomycin (medium). After

incubating for 24 hours, the medium was replaced with a solution comprising extracts and medium in a ratio of 20 μL extracts to 80 μL medium. The control group received a complete medium replacement. Following this, incubation continued for 1, 3, and 5 days. At the designated time points, the medium in each well was replaced with 100 μL of Alamar Blue working solution (consisting of 10% Alamar Blue in HBSS). Subsequently, the absorbance was recorded at 630 nm and 690 nm using a SpectraMax M3 multi-plate reader.

3. Results and Discussion

PCL was applied as a spray-coating onto glass slides, utilizing both ACE and DCM to assess which solvent would result in superior coating characteristics for the subsequent application of PCL to W/O samples. The FTIR spectra of the spray-coated PCL using ACE and DCM, along with their corresponding vibrations and assignments, are presented in Fig 2a. The notable peaks include 2900–3000 cm^{-1} for C–H₂ asymmetric stretching, 1700–1730 cm^{-1} for C=O stretching, 1460–1470 cm^{-1} for C–H scissoring and symmetric deformation, 1250 cm^{-1} for O–C–O asymmetric stretching, and 1150 cm^{-1} for C–O stretching. Upon observation of the FT–IR spectra, there were no significant differences between the spray-coated PCL via ACE and DCM.

Figure 2b illustrates the X-ray diffraction profiles of the spray-coated PCL. The diffraction pattern exhibits characteristic PCL peaks at 21.3° and 23.6°, corresponding to the (110) and (200) crystallographic planes, respectively [20]. Although there is a slight difference in peak intensities, the crystal form is largely the same for both solvents. The thermal behaviour of spray-coated PCL is displayed in Fig 3 where the degree of crystallinity is 32° and 30.2° for PCL sprayed via DCM and ACE, respectively. The DSC results confirm that the degree of crystallinity is higher for PCL applied using ACE. Also, the melting point for applied PCL using DCM is lower than the ACE-sprayed PCL. In fact, DCM has a lower boiling point and higher volatilization compared to acetone. When the volatilization of the solvent is very fast, PCL will solidify quickly, without enough time for crystallizing before solidification. Also, the melting point of the PCL formed by ACE is higher. Qin et al. showed that when solvent with a higher boiling point was used, PCL with a higher melting point was obtained [20]. As seen in Table 1, dissolving PCL in ACE needs heat, and the submerged PCL in ACE takes longer to dissolve than the floating PCL in DCM. However, it is noteworthy that, unlike DCM, ACE is non-toxic and not considered hazardous. The low boiling point of DCM poses a drawback, as it can lead to blockages in the spraying needle due to

overheating during the coating process. Overall, ACE proved to be more suitable for spray coating, leading to its selection for the subsequent coatings. Following the selection of acetone as the solvent, PCL was applied to glass slides over three different cycles. As illustrated in Fig 4a, an increase in the number of cycles resulted in higher coating roughness. But the difference in roughness between 60 and 90 cycles is less than the difference between 30 and 60 cycles. This is because when the PCL coating is being formed, rather than increasing the roughness and the thickness of the coating, microdroplets fill the cavities on the surface. In Fig 4b, the gloss intensity of the samples is shown. Compared to 150 GU for uncoated glass slides, by increasing the number of cycles, the opacity is decreased, meaning that the transparent PCL coating density is increasing and that the sprayed microdroplets are well dispersed on the surface. The PCL was then applied on the W/O samples to prepare W/O/P samples where PCL is formed on the oxide layer of WE43 samples.

As shown in Fig 5, the W/O surface (Fig 5a) is partially covered with the sprayed PCL after 30 cycles (Fig 5b). By increasing the cycle numbers, the PCL layer covers the W/O surface more effectively. Therefore, samples with a 90-cycle sprayed PCL were used for further investigations. According to Fig 6, the W/O sample has a lower contact angle compared to uncoated WE43 as the porous oxide layer absorbs water. Although the oxide layer improves the corrosion properties, the associated hydrophilicity is undesirable as it causes water uptake [16]. The applied PCL layer in three different cycles increased the contact angle to approximately 100°. This contact angle is achieved despite the surface roughness; thus, it is due to the hydrophobic nature of PCL, which is beneficial for corrosion behaviour.

Fig 7a shows the oxide layer formed on the WE43 with a 6.5 μm thickness. The sprayed PCL coating sealed the pores and filled the cavities on the oxide layer surface (see Fig 5). Therefore, the thickness of the PCL layer formed on the oxide layer cannot be distinguished. Thus, the same 90-cycle of PCL was applied on glass slides (Fig 7b) to establish the thickness. It can be seen that the W/O/P sample mainly contains Mg, O and C elements from the WE43 substrate, anodized layer and polymer layer. Fig 8a shows the mass loss of different samples after 144 hours of immersion in PBS, which is in accordance with the hydrogen formation results, as illustrated in Fig 8a. The hydrogen formed on the surface is significantly decreased for the W/O/P sample, indicating that the extent of corrosion had decreased and led to less mass loss on this sample. There is no significant change in the amount of formed hydrogen on the W/O/P sample after 72 hours of coating, whereas, for the W and W/O samples, hydrogen formation continues. As hydrogen is a by-product of corrosion occurring on the surface, it can be deduced

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra (a) and X-ray diffraction (b) of spray-coated PCL in ACE and DCM.

Table 1: Conditions for PCL to dissolve in different solvents.

Solvent	Density (g cm^{-3})	Boiling point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Dissolution temp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Dissolution Time (min)
ACE	0.79	56	50	15
DCM	1.33	39.6	Room temp	5
PCL	1.14	237	-	-

that the W/O/P sample is more resistant to corrosion than the other samples. Fig 9 shows the Mg 1s, O 1s, C 1s, Na 1s and P 2p XPS spectra of the surfaces of different samples after 7 days of immersion in PBS. The Mg 2s and O 1s spectra were detected at 88.8 and 531.8 eV, respectively. The presence of the peaks related to $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, which is a corrosion by-product, is shown to have lowest intensity for the W/O/P sample. Mg 2s peak related to W/O/P sample is almost negligible. The C 1s peak at 284.8 eV corresponds to adventitious carbon, and the peak at 286.5 eV may be associated with the presence of C-O groups. With respect to the results in Table 2, the topmost corrosion layer is mainly composed of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ for the W and W/O samples, and carbon species for the W/O/P sample. The presence of these species (Fig 9f), such as carbonates, has led to less corrosion and a reduced amount of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$.

Figure 3: DSC curves of spray-coated PCL using ACE and DCM.

Figure 4: Roughness (a) and gloss intensity (b) of the PCL-coated glass slides.

Figure 5: Microstructure of (a) W/O and PCL layer formed on W/O samples in (b) 30, (c) 60 and (d) 90 cycles of spray coating.

Table 2: Mass concentration (%) of XPS spectra from the surface of Al-treated samples.

Sample	Mg 2s	P 2p	C 1s	O 1s	Na 1s
W	8.40	16.10	14.53	49.48	9.27
W/O	13.36	15.26	10.57	45.24	7.08
W/O/P	2.29	4.63	61.29	28.54	2.30

Figure 6: Contact angles of uncoated WE43, W/O and PCL layer formed on W/O samples after different numbers of cycles of spray coating.

Figure 7: Cross-section images of (a) oxide layer formed on WE43 and (b) 90-cycle sprayed PCL on the glass slide. (c) Surface morphology of W/O/P and EDS mapping: Mg (d), C (e) and O (f).

Figure 8: a) Mass loss and b) cumulative hydrogen formed on different samples immersed in PBS solution at 37 °C for 144 hours.

Figure 9: XPS spectra of the corrosion by-products formed on the surface of different samples. (a) Mg 1s, (b) O 1s, (c) C 1s, (d) Na 1s, (e) P 2p, and (f) FT-IR spectra of different samples.

To investigate the status of samples in the corrosion medium further, we performed EIS tests on various samples during their immersion process in the PBS. The electrochemical impedance curves of the samples were analyzed by equivalent circuit fitting, and the fitting results are shown in Table 3. R_s is the resistance of PBS solution, and R_p and CPE_p are the PCL coating resistance and capacitance. R_o and CPE_o are the resistance and capacitance of the transition layer for the W/O sample and corrosion products passivation layer produced after immersion in PBS on the surface for the W sample. R_{ct} and CPE_{dl} represent the charge transfer resistance and double layer capacitance, respectively.

Fig.10a is the electrochemical impedance curves of different samples in PBS solution. It can be seen that W samples are more prone to corrosion compared to other samples. Its corresponding R_{ct} value is lower, which means that corrosion can occur easily. For the W/O sample, two capacitance loops are observed regarding the oxide transition layer and double layer mentioned in the fitting equivalent circuit (Fig.10c). For the W/O/P sample, the capacitance loops are merged and difficult to distinguish separately. Therefore, according to Fig.10b, it is seen that there are three different peaks for the W/O/P sample around 10^4 , 10^2 and 10^{-1} Hertz. R_p is not significant, which means that the sprayed PCL layer does not have high corrosion resistance. However, both the Nyquist and Bode plots show that the W/O/P sample has higher corrosion resistance. The W/O/P curve has bigger capacitance loops, and in the Bode plot, it intercepts the $|Z|$ axis at higher values, meaning that the total corrosion resistance of the sample coated with PCL on top of its transition layer has the highest resistance against corrosion. This shows that the PCL in the form of micro-sized droplets has been able to cover the porous structure of the oxide transition layer, decreasing the solution uptake and increasing the corresponding corrosion resistance.

Fig.11 presents the stress-strain curves for different immersed samples versus WE43 and the flexural modulus of different samples. The surfaces of these samples after 7 days of immersion and immediately before the three-point bending test are shown in Fig.12. It is seen that the W sample has undergone general corrosion on the surface, whereas, for the W/O sample, there are only some corrosion sites. However, the oxide layer on the W/O/P sample remains intact, and no corrosion site is seen on the surface. The corrosion resistance of the W/O/P sample is superior, and the EIS and mass loss test previously confirmed this. Thus, the mechanical properties measured via a three-point bending test can be analyzed in terms of the corrosion associated with each sample. Compared to WE43,

Table 3: The fitting results of EIS on different samples.

Sample	R_s ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	R_p ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	CPE_{p-1} ($\text{Sn} \cdot \text{Q}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	N_p	R_o ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	CPE_{o-1} ($\text{Sn} \cdot \text{Q}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	no	R_{ct} ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	CPE_{dl-1} ($\text{Sn} \cdot \text{Q}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	ndl
W	35.97	-	-	-	2615	1.58×10^{-5}	0.89	959.4	1.2×10^{-4}	0.82
W/O	35.78	-	-	-	4729	1.37×10^{-5}	0.83	2684	4.3×10^{-4}	0.79
W/O/P	35.31	126.3	6.54×10^{-6}	0.73	4521	1.63×10^{-6}	0.64	5547	1.4×10^{-4}	0.90

Figure 10: a) Nyquist, b) Bode plots and equivalent circuits for c) W and W/O samples and d) W/O/P samples immersed in PBS solution.

Figure 11: a) Stress-strain curve, and b) flexural modulus of different samples immersed in PBS solution for 7 days compared to WE4.

immersed samples have a lower flexural modulus, which is due to the extent of corrosion that happens on each sample. The W/O/P sample has a higher flexural modulus and UTS than the W and W/O samples, indicating that the oxide layer coupled with PCL coating has protected the mechanical integrity.

Fig.12a shows the surface of bare WE43 after 7-days immersion in PBS: it has undergone corrosion generally, and the corrosion products can be seen all across the surface. According to Table 4, crystalline structures are corrosion products that can be calcium and phosphorus depositions from PBS, as well as oxides. These corrosion products shift the corrosion potential toward passive values and help to resist against corrosion. For the W/O sample in Fig.12b, there are partial deposits of Ca and P, but there is no evident corrosion site on the surface. The W/O/P sample in Fig.12c is not much different to that shown in Fig.5c as it has remained intact during immersion in PBS. A homogeneous PCL layer can be seen on the surface, protecting it against corrosion. This suggests that the bonding of PCL to the oxide layer is strong since the extent of C present on the surface is considerable. It is important to note that the O content is not only indicative of the corrosion extent in these three samples. O in the W sample is due to corrosion on the surface. Still, for the W/O and W/O/P samples, O is related to the oxide layer formed by anodization, which PCL covers in the W/O/P sample, and it is for this reason that there is a lower O extent in this sample.

Figure 12: a) W, b) W/O, and c) W/O/P samples immersed in PBS solution for 7 days.

Table 4: EDS elemental quantitative data representative of different samples immersed in PBS for 7 days.

Sample	Mg	O	C	P	Ca	BAL
W	23.15	58.18	-	15.98	2.33	0.36
W/O	18.83	53.31	-	15.29	10.77	1.80
W/O/P	15.52	33.32	49.52	-	0.90	0.74

As PCL showed strong bonding after 7-day immersion in PBS, to evaluate the adhesion, a cross-cut tape test was performed on the W/O/P sample, the results of which are seen in Fig.13a. EDS mapping was performed to see where the PCL detached from the surface. As seen in Fig.13c, Mg is present only in the cuts, meaning that the cuts are deep enough to reach the WE43 substrate and yet no Mg between the cuts. Fig.13c and Fig.13d show that the cuts have removed both O and C from the surface. However, the cut lines are wider in Fig.13c than Fig.13d, which means the PCL is detached around the cut lines, which is also evident in Fig.13b, although the oxide layer is intact. Overall, the adhesion of PCL is good since less than 10% C is detached from the surface.

The results depicting cell viabilities in the extracts-medium mixtures solution for 1, 3, and 5 days are presented in Fig.14. Following 1 day of culturing, no significant difference was observed among all samples when compared with the control group. At this stage, all samples exhibited robust cell viability. However, a notable decline in cell viability was observed after 3 and 5 days, attributable to the release of Mg^{2+} and changes in pH. After three days of culturing, the cell viabil-

Figure 13: a) Optical microscope and b) SEM and map distribution of c) Mg, d) C and e) O of cross cuts on W/O/P sample.

Figure 14: In vitro cell viability of HAoEC cultured in the extracts-medium mixtures solution for 1, 3, and 5 days for different samples

ity of group W declined rapidly (to c. 60%), displaying a significant difference compared with the control group ($p < 0.0001$). Conversely, group W/O exhibited better viability (i.e., c. 70%) than group W and also showed a significant difference from the control group ($p < 0.01$). Notably, the cell viability of group W/P/O remained around 80%, surpassing that of groups W and W/O. However, by day 5, the cell viability of all samples exhibited a significant difference compared with the control group (i.e., cell viability reduced to c. 50%). These findings underscore the impact of Mg^{2+} release and pH changes on cell viability over extended culturing periods. Overall, the W/O/P sample shows higher cell viability compared to other samples.

4. Conclusion

An innovative ultrasonic atomization spray coating method was used to coat PCL directly onto the surface of WE43. This novel technique involved the use of two distinct common solvents, and a comparative analysis was undertaken to ascertain the superior solvent for the coating process. This investigation has sought to determine the most effective and efficient solvent for achieving optimal results in the PCL coating on the WE43 surface. Acetone was chosen over dichloromethane. The following conclusions can be made:

- While both acetone and dichloromethane are viable options for ultrasonic spray coating of PCL, acetone is the preferred solvent due to several advantages. Dichloromethane, with its lower boiling point, poses an increased risk of evaporating in the heated nozzle, potentially impacting the coating process. Additionally, dichloromethane is considered hazardous compared to acetone, further substantiating the preference for the latter in this application.
- The oxide layer plays a crucial role in preserving the integrity of the PCL coating on WE43. Its porous microstructure not only enhances the bonding between the polymer and the metal but also serves as a mitigating factor against hydrogen formation and, consequently, corrosion. This dual functionality effectively prevents the PCL coating from undesired peeling or deterioration. Thus, the oxide layer, with its porous characteristics, emerges as a key contributor to the overall durability and stability of the PCL coating on the WE43 substrate.

- PCL coating has proven key to augmenting both the corrosion resistance and biocompatibility of WE43. Functioning as an additional barrier against corrosion, PCL, which is inherently hydrophobic, significantly reduces water uptake. Furthermore, it acts to seal the porous oxide layer, leading to a remarkable increase in corrosion resistance compared to uncoated WE43. This heightened resistance translates into substantially less degradation of the material, contributing to a more stable pH environment, which correlates with enhanced cell viability.

In future work, other methods such as laser ablation and PEO will be used for modifying the surface as well, and the results will be compared for the highest bonding adhesion and corrosion resistance while maintaining cell viability for an ideal biodegradable gene or drug-eluting platform.

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